

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Demographic Factors and their impact on Consumer Attitude towards Green Durable Products in Delhi/NCR

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Abstract

Demographic factors are considered the basic factors of any study because these factors laid the foundation for other important factors. It has been noticed that demographic factors are the important factors influencing consumer environmental behavior. However, sometimes the role of demographic factors which makes any research a subject of criticism therefore this research will also try to discuss the impact of demographic factors in forming consumer attitudes toward green durable products. The present study will also focus on green durable products as India is considered the largest consumer durable product market in the world. Due to environmental- issues, businesses are now a day trying to be compatible with a sustainable development approach and moving towards green marketing. As a sign of conclusion, green products coming in the light and consumers are going towards the same with an understanding that these products can have the solution to environmental problems. Therefore, to know the consumers' understanding towards the same demographic factors have more significance. To fulfill the purpose of the study primary data will be collected from the 252 respondents through a well – structured Likert scaled questionnaire. The sample is selected with the help of a simple random sampling method. Descriptive and inferential statistics will be used to prove the hypotheses of the study with help of SPSS software (version 26).

Keywords: Sustainable Development; Green Products; Green Consumer Durable Products; Demographic factors; Consumer Attitude; Green Consumer Behavior

1. Introduction

In the era of sustainable development various environmental issues such as pollution, global warming, deforestation, depletion of natural resources, etc., have been noticed. These environmental issues may directly or indirectly affect the life and health of people on the planet due to people is trying to make changes in their lifestyles. In their life style socio-demographic variables also have a prominent effect regarding their consumption habits of goods and services. Eventually, the scenario has been getting changed along with the adoption of sustainable development approaches in the process of production to marketing of goods and services. As a result, a new form of marketing has been introduced which is known as green marketing with the inception of the green product. These products are environmentally friendly products with less detrimental impact on the environment. Consumer durable products industries also get influenced by sustainable marketing approaches and trying to provide the products in the form of green consumer durable products like consumer electronics and consumer appliances.

But it is not necessary that green products will become consumer demand so sometimes it is necessary to know the consumers' attitude towards green durable products. Attitude refers to someone's inner feeling or perception to show whether the individual likes or dislikes something [1]. Attitude can be defined as feelings that are beneficial or disliked

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towards characteristics of the physical environment or related problems. The present study is based on the consumers of Delhi/NCR by adding some variables related to consumers' attitudes in terms of green durable products.

Objective of the Study

- To understand the role of demographic factors (age, gender, income, occupation, education and residence) on consumer attitude for green durable products.
- To find out the factors affecting consumer attitude towards green durable products.
- To find out the relationship between Consumers' demographic factors and their attitude towards green durable products.
- To find out the impact of Consumers' demographic factors on their attitude towards green durable products.

2. Review of Literature

2.1. Demographic Factors

2.1.1. Gender

Clare D'Souza et al., 2018 study have identified that men are more aware about environmental issues, whereas women are more concerned about environmental quality [2]. Research has also specified that the higher educational level and social class, related to greater environmental knowledge. The findings also suggested that female was the highly socially conscious person and younger individual are more sensitive to the environmental issues. The study of Adu-Fosu, A. P. (2020) revealed that demographic factors performed a major role in the purchase behavior of green products and male respondents are dominant users of green products [3]. Many studies revealed that there is a difference in the behavior of men and women where women are more positive than men toward green concepts (Tikka et al., 2000; Stern et al., 1993; Zelezny et al., 2000). Many studies show that there is a difference in behavior of men and women where women are having more positive behavior than men towards green concepts [4] [5] [6].

2.1.2. Age

Young consumers liked to use green products as compared to other age categories. Maichum et al., (2017) concluded that young age respondents are more concerned about the environment and their purchase behavior and their environmental attitude depends upon the same [7].

Ottman et al. (2006) highlighted that young age people are more adaptive toward new and innovative ideas in comparison of old age people. D'Souza et al. 2007 found that the results of younger and older age groups towards concerning with environmental issues are contradicted to each other [8]. Consumers who are below 20 years old have stronger perceptions of environmental factors compared to adults (Wang et al 2022) [9].

The age segment between 25-34 years and 45-54 years of respondents are more interested in green movements (Fisher et al 2012). Older consumers are more likely to be concerned about environmental issues and be more attentive to green labeling (C.D' Souza et al 2007) [10].

2.1.3. Marital Status

Fisher et al (2012) highlighted that married respondents are more attentive to purchasing green products. Married respondents have shown positive intentions to buy green products. Married people are more likely to exhibit environmentally friendly behaviors [11]. Patel, et al., (2017) found in their research that married consumers have more pro-environmental behavior than the single consumers (Patel et al, 2017) [12]. However marital status sometime found to be a non-relevant factor that correlates with environmental behavior (Kalaiselvi & Dhinakaran 2021) [13].

2.1.4. Education

(Haron and et al 2005) Formally educated respondents are more capable to understand green products and respondents with high income performed well in favor of green products [14]. DiPietro et al., (2013) study revealed that female customers and highly educated people were more conscious about green practices. They also pay attention to promoting green products [15]. D'Souza et al., (2007) [16] believe that environmental concerns are directly related to a consumer's level of education. Fisher et al (2012) [17] revealed that higher levels of education were more likely to exhibit environmentally friendly behaviors. The level of education increases environmental consciousness and the

maturity level of the people as well (Prasher 2020) [18]. Highly educated respondents are more interested in purchasing organic or green products than the lower - educated respondents (Wee et al, 2014)[19].

2.1.5 Occupation

Dubey and Shukla (2004) in their study concluded that students and professionals are positive towards environmental issues. They tend to perform both participatory and leadership actions for the conservation of the environment[20]. Professionals have shown their much intention to buy green products[21]. Sorvali (2023) found students and professionals are more environmentally concerned which reflects in their pro-environmental behavior, especially in India (Sorvali 2023) [22]. Kumar & et al (2021) found in his research that employed peoples are more concerned about the environment and their level of environment knowledge and awareness is higher than that of ordinary people [23].

2.1.6 Income

Consumers who have higher income are more in favor of a positive perception towards the green concept than the lower income consumers (Rezai et al 2013) [24]. Respondents who have income between 4 lakhs to 6 lakhs have shown more positive intention to buy green products (Gauncar & et al) [25]. Higher- income group respondents are more inclined to purchase green organic products (Wee 2014) [26]. Study stated that respondents with higher level of income are more concerned with environmental issues (Fisher 2012) [27].

2.1.7 Residence

Savita (2014) concluded that north Indian people especially Delhites, are more aware and sensitive towards environmental issues as they buy more environment-friendly products. Fly and Cordell (1999) [28] indicates no significant difference urban and rural residents of the region on issues related to the environment. Buttel & Flinn (1978) [29] found urban consumers are found more aware of environmental problems than rural consumers.

2.2. Factors of Consumer Attitude towards green products

2.2.1. Environmental Concern (EC)

The importance of environmental concern is associated with the difference in consumer attitude and it is insignificant based on the gender and age of the respondents (Singh and Bansal, 2012) [30]. Kirmani and Khan (2015)[31] indicated that the environment has a positive influence on consumer attitude. Environmental concern is one of the important variables to form consumer attitudes toward green products. One of the studies revealed that environmental concern is a critical factor to influence consumer attitudes toward green products (Yang, 2017) [32].

2.2.2. Environmental Awareness (EA)

Consumers' pro-environmental behavior, and psychographic characteristics such as knowledge, awareness, and values are influencing factors in making consumers' attitudes (Anvar and Venter 2014) [33]. Environmental awareness is positively associated with consumer attitude toward green products which reflect in various liking and disliking of green products (Indriani et al 2019)[34].

2.2.3. Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE)

Perceived Consumer Effectiveness is an important predictor of consumer attitude (Tan 2011) [35]. Perceived Consumer Effectiveness was considered a measure of the attitude of the consumer and was also modeled as a direct predictor of environmentally friendly behaviors (Nath et al 2013) [36]. Perceived Consumer Effectiveness can increase the consumer understanding that they make by going green (Gleim & Lawson 2014) [37].

2.2.4. Social Norms (SN)

Dempsey et al (2018) [38] believe that social norms and a person's attitude have a close relationship. Megens & Weerman (2010) also believe that the impact of social norms and other peer-related factors on attitude is translated into our behavior [39]. Scholars such as Dewanto & Belgiawan (2020) believe that social norms are closely related to consumer attitude towards green products [40]. Social norms are the important variables that affect consumer sustainable behavior in the context of solving environmental problems and challenges (Ogiemwonyi, et al 2019) [41].

Figure 1 Proposed Model of the Study

(Source: Figure created by author on the basis of literature review)

Hypotheses of the Study

- **H01:** There is no significant difference between Gender and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H02:** There is no significant difference between Age and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H03:** There is no significant difference between Marital Status and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H04:** There is no significant difference between Income and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H05:** There is no significant difference between Occupation and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H06:** There is no significant difference between Educational Qualification and Factors of Consumers' Attitude towards green durable products.
- **H07:** There is no significant difference between factors of Consumers' Attitude and Attitude of Consumers towards green durable products.
- **H08:** There is no impact of factors of Consumers' Attitude and Attitude of consumers towards green durable products.

3. Research Methodology

The study is exploratory and descriptive and its main purpose is to find out the role and impact of demographic factors on consumer attitudes toward green durable products. The questions were asked to the respondents related with their demographic profile and factors forming consumers' attitudes (environmental concern, environmental awareness, perceived consumer effectiveness, and social norms) towards green durable products.

3.1. Data Collection Technique

The data was collected through both primary and secondary data collection techniques. A closed ended structural questionnaire was set up to collect the primary data. The primary data was collected through a closed-ended structured questionnaire. The data collection based on the Google form and direct interview from the people.

3.2. Designing the questionnaire

The questionnaire was designed in such a way that the hypotheses of the study could be tested. The questionnaire included closed-ended Likert scale questions from strongly agree to strongly disagree ranging from 1 to 5.

3.3. The Sampling design

A Simple random sampling method was used to select the data. As per this sampling method, each member of the population has an equal opportunity to be chosen in the sample. The sample size is 252 respondents collected for the study from Delhi/NCR.

3.4. Data Analysis Methods

Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used for data analysis. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used for data analysis. For descriptive analysis percentage and mean analysis were used to analyze the demographic information of the respondents. In the case of the inferential statistics KMO and Bartlet test, ANOVA, and Regression were used to analyze the hypothesis of the study.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of the Respondents

Items	Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	107	42.5
	Male	145	57.5
Age	15-25 years	75	29.8
	26-35 years	90	35.7
	36-45 years	53	21.0
	46 years and Above	34	13.5
Marital Status	Single	117	46.4
	Married	135	53.6
Educational Qualification	No Formal Qualifications & Less than Secondary	35	13.9
	Secondary to Higher Secondary	34	13.5
	Undergraduate	29	11.5
	Graduate	84	33.3
	Post Graduate and Above	70	27.8
Occupation	Students	45	17.9
	Unemployed	18	7.1
	Govt. Employed	50	19.8
	Private. Employed	62	24.6
	Self - Employed	34	13.5
	Home Makers	43	17.1
Income (Monthly)	Up-to Rs. 10,000	43	17.1
	Rs.11,000-Rs.50,000	107	42.5
	Rs.51000-Rs.1,00,000	50	19.8
	More Than Rs.1,00,000	52	20.6
Residence	Delhi	64	17.7
	Noida	49	13.5

	Ghaziabad	49	13.5
	Faridabad	43	11.9
	Gurgaon	47	13.0
	Total	252	100.0

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data collection)

According to the above-mentioned demographic characteristics table of the respondents, 57.5 percent were male and 42.5 percent were female respondents who participated in the survey. The survey revealed that respondents were 33.3 percent the graduate in majority, 11.5 percent the under-graduate, 27.8 percent postgraduate and above, 13.5 percent of Secondary to Higher Secondary, and 13.9 percent with no formal education.

46.4 percent of respondents surveyed were single, and 53.6 percent of respondents were married. 29.8 percent of respondents were 15-25 years, 35.7 percent of respondents were 26-35 years, 21.0 percent of respondents were from 36-45 years, and 13.5 percent of the respondents were from 46 years and above. It is shown that the vast majority of the respondents were from the 26-35 years of age group.

17.1 percent Up to income of Rs. 10,000, 42.5 percent respondents comprised of Rs.11,000-Rs.50,000 monthly income, 19.8 percent respondents comprised of Rs.51,000-Rs.1,00,000 monthly income and 20.6 percent of the respondents with More than Rs.1,00,000. In this case, the vast majority of respondents surveyed consumers' income consisted of middle – level income group. Occupations of the respondents were Students, Unemployed, Govt.-employed, Pvt.-employed, Self-employed, and Homemakers with 17.9, 7.1, 19.8, 24.6, 13.5, and 17.1 percent respectively. Most of the respondents were privately employed. The majority of the respondents were from Delhi i.e., 17.7 percent as compared to NCR respondents (See Table 1).

Table 2 KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.			0.758
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square		58.295
	df		6
	Sig.		0.000

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The given table explains the factor loading for factors of consumer attitude for green durable products. KMO is 0.758 which is higher than 0.6, Bartlett test is significant and the data shows highly appropriate for data analysis. It also reflect correlation between variables (See Table 2).

Table 3 Communalities for Factors’ of Consumer Attitude

Communalities for Factors’ of Consumer Attitude		
	Initial	Extraction
EC1	1.000	0.685
EC2	1.000	0.628
EC3	1.000	0.645
EC4	1.000	0.360
EA1	1.000	0.640
EA2	1.000	0.659
EA3	1.000	0.619
EA4	1.000	0.483

PCE1	1.000	0.619
PCE2	1.000	0.550
PCE3	1.000	0.962
PCE4	1.000	0.962
SN1	1.000	0.695
SN2	1.000	0.535
SN4	1.000	0.576
SN4	1.000	0.644
ATT1	1.000	0.548
ATT2	1.000	0.563
ATT3	1.000	0.672
ATT4	1.000	0.504
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table showed the communalities extraction based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA). All the variables have a value greater than 0.5 signifying substantial portion of the variance in the variables is accounted for by the factors (See Table 3).

4.2. ANOVA Analysis

4.2.1. Hypothesis 1

Table 4 ANOVA Analysis for Gender of the respondents

Variables	Gender	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	Female	54.5070	107	4.89879	1	2.249	0.135
	Male	55.2483	145	2.90675			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is no significant difference between gender ($F=2.249$, $P=0.135$) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus, the hypothesis is supported. Since the p-value is more than 0.05% and the mean value depicts that males are having more positive consumer attitude towards green products (see table no 4).

4.2.2. Hypothesis 2

Table 5 ANOVA Analysis for Age of the respondents

Variables	Age	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	15-25 years	55.2567	75	3.71901	3	0.260	0.854
	26-35 years	54.8556	90	3.29666			
	36-45 years	54.7642	53	5.16539			
	46 years and Above	54.6912	34	3.50003			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is no significant difference between age ($F=0.260$, $P=0.854$) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus hypothesis is supported. Since the p-value is more than 0.05% and the mean value depicted that the age group of 15-25 years are having more positive consumer attitude towards green durable products (see table no 5).

4.2.3. Hypothesis 3

Table 6 ANOVA Analysis for Marital Status of the respondents

Variables	Marital Status	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	Single	55.4145	117	3.02738	1	3.374	0.067
	Married	54.5167	135	4.47268			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is no significant difference between marital status ($F=3.374$, $P=0.067$) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus, the hypothesis is supported. Since the p-value is more than 0.05% and the mean value depicted that single respondents are having positive consumer attitude towards green durable products (see table no 6).

4.2.4. Hypothesis 4

Table 7 ANOVA Analysis for Educational Qualification of the respondents

Variables	Educational Qualification	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	No Formal Qualifications & Less than Secondary	55.1214	35	6.06077	4	2.110	0.009
	Secondary to Higher Secondary	55.2132	34	2.37261			
	Undergraduate	54.7328	29	5.40541			
	Graduate	54.9405	84	3.03881			
	Post Graduate and Above	54.7786	70	3.33692			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is a significant difference between educational qualification ($F=2.110$, 0.009) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected. Since the p-value is less than 0.05%. Graduate consumers are highly statistically significant at 5% and the consumers of Postgraduate and above are also statistically significant. The study also reflected that as the level of education is increasing the consumers' attitude toward green durable products (see table no 7).

4.2.5. Hypothesis 5

Table 8 ANOVA Analysis for Occupation of the respondents

Variables	Occupation	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	Students	55.1167	45	3.42849	5	3.723	0.007
	Unemployed	55.1389	18	1.75361			
	Govt. Employed	55.5800	50	3.06080			
	Private Employed	55.0121	62	3.20330			
	Self Employed	54.3309	34	3.33696			

	Home Makers	54.2674	43	6.39461			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is a significant difference between occupation ($F=3.723$, 0.007) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected. Since the p-value is less than 0.05%. Govt. Employed and Private Employed consumers are highly statistically significant at 5%. Students are also statistically significant towards factors of consumer attitude for green durable products. Hence rejected the null hypothesis (see table no 8).

4.2.6. Hypothesis 6

Table 9 ANOVA Analysis for Monthly Income of the respondents

Variables	Monthly Income	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	Upto Rs. 10,000	55.2674	43	4.19835	3	0.411	0.745
	Rs.11,000-Rs.50,000	54.8014	107	4.09149			
	Rs.51000-Rs.1,00,000	54.5800	50	3.41457			
	More Than Rs.1,00,000	55.2692	52	3.67685			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is no significant difference between the monthly income of the respondents ($F=0.411$, $P=0.745$) and consumer attitude towards green durable products. This hypothesis is supported. Since the p-value is more than 0.05%. However, the mean value depicted income group up-to Rs.10,000/- are having positive consumer attitude towards green durable products (see table no 9).

4.2.7. Hypothesis 7

Table 10 ANOVA Analysis for Residence of the respondents

Variables	Residence	Mean	N	S. D.	df	F	P
Factors of Consumer Attitude	Delhi	54.5352	64	4.10378	4	0.662	0.619
	Noida	55.1020	49	2.67362			
	Ghaziabad	54.4949	49	5.30735			
	Faridabad	55.1860	43	3.44432			
	Gurgaon	55.5266	47	3.29576			
	Total	54.9335	252	3.88804			

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

The above table indicated that there is no significant difference between the residence of the respondents ($F=0.662$, $P=0.619$) and factors of consumer attitude towards green durable products. Thus, the hypothesis is supported. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05%. However, the mean value depicted that respondents of Noida, Faridabad and Gurgaon are having positive consumer attitude towards green durable products (see table no.10).

4.2.8. Hypothesis 8: Regression Analysis

Table 11 Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.338 ^a	0.114	0.100	1.743
a. Predictors: (Constant), SN AVG, EA AVG, PCE AVG, EC AVG				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	96.780	4	24.195	7.966	0.000 ^b
	Residual	750.204	247	3.037		
	Total	846.984	251			
a. Dependent Variable: Attitude AVG						
b. Predictors: (Constant), SN AVG, EA AVG, PCE AVG, EC AVG						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.931	1.880		5.283	0.000
	EC AVG	0.009	0.075	0.008	0.121	0.904
	EA AVG	0.135	0.068	0.132	1.999	0.047
	PCE AVG	0.246	0.053	0.288	4.680	0.000
	SN AVG	0.008	0.064	0.008	0.131	0.896
a. Dependent Variable: Attitude AVG						

(Source: Table created by Author on the basis of data analysis)

4.3. Interpretation

The above table indicated that Model summary indicating that four independent variables are entered into the regression model to correlate with the dependent variable where R is representing the high degree positive correlation between the dependent and independent variables with Regression coefficient value (R=.0338). The R square value is 0.114 taking into account all four independent variables which are concluding that .100 percent (Adjust R square) of variances of consumer attitude was explained in this model (see table no.11).

5. Result and Discussion

The current study indicated that demographic factors performed a prominent role in making consumer attitudes regarding green durable products. Felix, et al., (2022) [42] study showed that males are good observant towards green durable products and the present study also proved the same. This study also revealed that mature-aged married are greatly observant towards green durable products, the study supported by Ali, Jony, & Shakil (2017)[43] concluded that educated and aware people are more interested in following the 'Green Concept'. This study also revealed that employed people are more influenced by the factors of consumers' attitudes. The current study also emphasized that the middle-

income group thinks about green durable products and changed their attitude towards the same. The study revealed that respondents of Delhi are more influenced by the factors of consumers' attitudes.

6. Conclusion

The study revealed that demographic factors played a major role in making consumer attitudes toward green durable products. The study also revealed that demographic factors are highly correlated with consumers' environmental concerns, environmental awareness, perceived consumer effectiveness, and social norms. These factors assist consumers to make their attitude regarding green durable products. The study revealed that matured aged-married-males are more cognitive towards factors of consumer attitude. The study also indicated that education and income played a prominent role and counted as important demographic factors in making consumer attitudes. In regards to geographic location or residence, the people of NCR are more influenced by factors of consumers' attitudes in comparison to Delhi.

The study also highlighted that demographic factors performed an important role in consumer attitude. According to Schiffman's and Kanuk' (2010) attitude theory, the positive attitude of consumers toward objects is followed by positive behaviors [44]. This attitude refers to psychological tendencies expressed by evaluating certain entities with several levels of like or dislike.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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